

IMPACTS OF POVERTY ALLEVIATION PROGRAMMES IN ESAN WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, EDO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This research work was conducted to investigate the impact of poverty alleviation programmes in Esan West Local Government Area of Edo State, South-South region Nigeria. It examined the impact of the programmes on household income, employment opportunities, and living standards of beneficiaries in the region. It identified inadequate funding, corruption, and inefficiencies in programme implementation as major challenges confronting the implementation of poverty alleviation programmes in the South-South region, with Esan West Local Government Area as case study. Research questions and hypotheses were raised to guide the study. The study adopted a survey design which involves the use of structured questionnaire to collect data from diverse groups of respondents, including programme beneficiaries, community leaders, and policymakers. The total population of the study was estimated at one hundred and eighty-eight thousand, seven hundred (188, 700). Taro Yamane formula was used for determining the sample size and response rate of 60% was adopted for analysis. The result of the findings revealed that poverty alleviation programmes have not substantially improved household income among beneficiaries; poverty alleviation programmes were perceived as moderately effective in creating employment opportunities; and skills acquisition initiatives were noted as particularly important in enhancing employability; corruption and mismanagement of funds were rated as significant obstacles. The study recommended that the government should prioritise increased and consistent funding for poverty alleviation programmes; incorporating community members in the planning, implementation, and monitoring of poverty alleviation programmes is crucial.

Keywords: Poverty Alleviation; Poverty Elimination; Poverty Dimension; Human Capital.

Introduction

Poverty remains a major socio-economic issue in Nigeria, despite the country's abundant natural resources and position as Africa's largest economy. The World Bank (2022) estimates about 40% of Nigeria's population lives below the poverty line of \$1 per day, with more classified as living just above it. Various factors contribute to this widespread poverty, including economic instability, high unemployment rates, inadequate infrastructure, and limited access to quality education and healthcare. In rural areas, these issues are often magnified by limited government support and insufficient employment opportunities (International Labour Organisation, 2021).

To combat poverty, the Nigerian government introduced numerous poverty alleviation programmes over the years. Examples include the National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP), launched in 2001, which focuses on areas like youth employment, rural infrastructure development, and social welfare support (Akpan, 2019). Other initiatives, such as the Conditional Cash Transfer programme (CCTP), were created to provide financial aid to low-income households, particularly in rural communities (Oseni, 2020). These programmes are generally impactful as they face various challenges which include insufficient funding, weak infrastructure, and operational inefficiencies (Bello & Oyinlola, 2019).

Within Edo State, and specifically in Esan West Local Government Area (LGA), poverty levels remain high, exacerbated by factors such as limited access to education, healthcare, and employment opportunities. Esan West is primarily rural, with a significant portion of its population reliant on agriculture. However, challenges like limited access to modern agricultural inputs, poor road infrastructure, and inconsistent access to markets restrict the economic productivity of many households (Edo State Bureau of Statistics, 2021).

Poverty alleviation programmes in Esan West Local Government Area is aimed at addressing these barriers, through the provision of financial resources, training, and support to promote self-employment and skills acquisition. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2021) said that initiative like these "...should be to build an open, efficient,

effective and globally competitive, integrated and collaborative environment in Africa that will facilitate the development and growth of humanitarian investment”. These initiatives often target women, youth, and farmers, who are among the most economically vulnerable. For instance, the N-Power programmes offer skill acquisition and training for young people, enabling them to become self-employed or gain meaningful employment in different sectors (Ojo & Adeyemi, 2021). Despite these efforts, it remains uncertain whether such programmes effectively reduce poverty and improve the living standards of beneficiaries.

Several challenges continue to undermine the potential success of these programmes. Funding limitations, implementation inefficiencies, and issues with accountability have often led to unmet programme objectives and limited reach (Onyeiwu, 2019). Corruption and bureaucratic delays further hinder the timely delivery of resources and support to intended beneficiaries, reducing the effectiveness of poverty alleviation efforts. Additionally, the absence of sufficient data to measure the outcomes of these programmes prevents the government and stakeholders from gaining clear insights into what works and where improvement is needed (Usman, 2020).

This study, therefore, seeks to investigate the effectiveness of poverty alleviation programmes within Esan West Local Government Area by examining their impact on household income, employment levels, and general well-being. It will also assess the challenges that inhibit these programmes’ success and offer recommendations for enhancing their efficacy. Through this analysis, the study aims to provide valuable insights for policymakers, helping to shape more impactful and sustainable poverty alleviation strategies in Esan West and other similar rural communities in Nigeria.

Esan West Local Government Area is a rural administrative region in Edo State, Nigeria, with a population primarily engaged in agricultural activities such as farming and trading. This Local Government Area is characterised by its economic reliance on subsistence agriculture, as well as its infrastructural challenges and limited access to quality healthcare and education services. In this study, Esan West Local Government Area serves as the geographical focus for assessing the impact of poverty alleviation programmes.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study is built upon the understanding of poverty as a multidimensional phenomenon, the mechanisms and strategies of poverty alleviation programmes, and the indicators used to evaluate their effectiveness. This framework provides a comprehensive basis for investigating poverty alleviation programmes in Esan West Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria, offering insights into how these initiatives address the diverse challenges associated with poverty.

Poverty and Its Dimensions

Poverty is among the most pressing challenges impeding global development and human well-being. It is not merely a lack of income but a multidimensional condition characterised by the absence of access to basic human needs, including adequate food, shelter, healthcare, education, and social inclusion. According to the World Bank (2022), poverty is defined in monetary terms as living on less than \$2.15 per day, a benchmark reflecting the minimum income required to sustain a basic standard of living. However, this monetary definition does not fully capture the complexity of poverty, which encompasses social and structural inequalities.

In Nigeria, poverty remains pervasive and entrenched, with over 40% of the population living below the national poverty line as of 2022 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022). The country's poverty rates vary across regions and demographics, with rural areas experiencing higher levels of deprivation than urban centres. This disparity is often attributed to limited access to essential services, infrastructural deficiencies, and reduced economic opportunities in rural communities. For instance, rural regions frequently lack adequate schools, healthcare facilities, and transportation infrastructure, further isolating these populations from opportunities for upward mobility (Bello & Oyinlola, 2019).

The multidimensional nature of poverty is increasingly recognised in global frameworks such as the global Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI), developed by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and the Oxford Poverty and Human

Development Initiative. The MPI assesses poverty beyond income, considering deprivations in health, education, and living standards. These dimensions provide a more holistic view of poverty and highlight its deep interconnections with social, economic, and institutional factors (UNDP, 2021). Thus, agencies are putting measures in place to manage and focus on concerned groups, for the purpose of getting results from target groups by deploying resources for efficient and effective development of collaborative partnership with interested parties or stakeholders (Oaikhena and Aligbe, 2023).

Challenges of poverty alleviation programmes in Nigeria

Despite their significant potential to reduce poverty and improve living conditions, poverty alleviation programmes in Nigeria encounter numerous challenges that undermine their effectiveness. These challenges are multifaceted, stemming from systemic issues such as corruption, inadequate funding, poor targeting, and logistical inefficiencies. Addressing these obstacles is essential to maximise the impact of such programmes and ensure they reach the intended beneficiaries.

One of the most pervasive challenges is corruption and mismanagement, which have deeply rooted impacts on poverty alleviation initiatives. Corruption leads to the diversion of resources intended for beneficiaries, undermining public trust and reducing the effectiveness of these programmes. For instance, funds allocated for skill acquisition schemes or cash transfers are often misappropriated, depriving vulnerable groups of the support they need. Bello and Oyinlola (2019) argue that corruption in Nigeria not only diminishes the impact of these interventions but also creates a sense of disillusionment among citizens, discouraging participation in government-led initiatives.

Another critical issue is inadequate funding, which limits the scope and scale of poverty alleviation programmes. Many initiatives are underfunded, reducing their capacity to reach all targeted populations, especially in rural areas where poverty is most concentrated. Budgetary constraints often lead to incomplete projects, poorly maintained infrastructure, and insufficient support for beneficiaries. Usman (2020) opines that even when programmes are well-designed, financial shortfalls can severely hamper their implementation resulting in fragmented and unsustainable outcomes. A related challenge

is the poor targeting of beneficiaries, which undermines the fundamental goal of poverty alleviation programmes to assist the most vulnerable populations. Weak data systems, limited transparency, and political interference often result in the exclusion of eligible beneficiaries while including non-eligible individuals. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2021) opined that “social protection is essential in addressing not only monetary poverty but also social exclusion”. For instance, programmes intended for low-income households may inadvertently benefit wealthier individuals due to inaccurate beneficiary identification processes (Akpan, 2019). This inefficiency not only wastes resources but also perpetuates inequality by failing to address the needs of the most disadvantaged groups.

Logistical and administrative challenges further compound the inefficiencies of poverty alleviation programmes. Delays in the disbursement of funds and materials, poor coordination among implementing agencies, and bureaucratic bottlenecks significantly hinder programme execution. These issues create inefficiencies that reduce the effectiveness of interventions and frustrate beneficiaries. Onyeiwu (2019) notes that such administrative inefficiencies often result in delays that diminish the intended benefits of programmes, particularly those aimed at providing timely support, such as agricultural inputs or conditional cash transfers. In addition to these systemic issues, poverty alleviation programmes in Nigeria also face challenges related to infrastructure and governance. Many rural areas lack the basic infrastructure required to support programme implementation, such as roads, reliable electricity, and communication networks. This not only increases the cost of delivering services but also limits the ability of beneficiaries to access and utilise programme resources effectively. Moreover, weak governance structures and the absence of accountability mechanisms exacerbate these challenges, allowing inefficiencies to persist unchecked (Babatunde et al., 2021).

The socio-political context in Nigeria further complicates poverty alleviation efforts. Ethnic and regional tensions, coupled with political interference, often result in an unequal distribution of resources. Programmes may be skewed in favour of politically connected individuals or regions, creating disparities in access to support. This politicisation of poverty alleviation efforts undermines their credibility and effectiveness,

leaving many deserving communities underserve. According to Oaikhena and Idehen (2021) they opined that “local government as a third-tier system of government in Nigeria was established to bring government closer to the people at the grass-root level”. Therefore, poverty alleviation programmes in Nigeria are critical tools for addressing widespread poverty, their impact is significantly diminished by challenges such as corruption, inadequate funding, poor targeting, and logistical inefficiencies. Addressing these obstacles requires comprehensive reforms, including improved transparency, better resource allocation, enhanced beneficiary identification systems, and stronger governance mechanisms. Only through such measures can poverty alleviation programmes fulfil their potential to uplift vulnerable populations and contribute to sustainable development in Nigeria.

Indicators of programme success

Evaluating the effectiveness of poverty alleviation programmes is crucial to determining their impact and sustainability. A successful programme can be identified by its ability to achieve its intended goals and deliver measurable outcomes that improve the quality of life for beneficiaries. The key indicators of programme success include household income, employment rates, living standards, social inclusion, and programme sustainability. These indicators provide a comprehensive framework for assessing the short- and long-term impacts of poverty alleviation initiatives in Nigeria, particularly in Esan West Local Government Area.

Theoretical Framework

A theoretical framework serves as the foundation for understanding and analysing the principles and mechanisms underlying poverty alleviation efforts. For this study, the Sustainable Livelihood Framework (SLF), Human Capital Theory, and Social Capital Theory provide critical perspectives on how poverty alleviation programmes can empower communities, foster development, and address the multifaceted challenges of poverty. These theories highlight different aspects of poverty and guide the design and evaluation of intervention programmes.

a. Sustainable Livelihood Framework (SLF)

The Sustainable Livelihood Framework (SLF), introduced by Chambers and Conway (1992), provides a comprehensive understanding of poverty by emphasising the resources and capabilities that individuals and households use to sustain their well-being. Unlike traditional income-based measures of poverty, the SLF recognises the multidimensional nature of livelihoods and the factors that enhance or hinder people's ability to sustain themselves. The SLF identifies five categories of livelihood assets that are critical to poverty reduction and they include human capital (skills, knowledge, and health), social capital (networks and relationships), natural capital (land, water, and biodiversity), physical capital (infrastructure and tools), and financial capital (income, savings, and credit). The framework also considers the vulnerability context, which includes economic shocks, climate variability, and other external pressures that exacerbate poverty. Policies, institutions, and processes are highlighted as essential components that influence access to assets and the effectiveness of livelihood strategies.

This framework is highly relevant to poverty alleviation programmes in Esan West Local Government Area, where many residents rely on subsistence farming and face infrastructure deficits. For example, interventions like rural infrastructure development under the National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP) aim to strengthen physical and natural capital by improving access to irrigation, roads, and markets. Similarly, skill acquisition initiatives contribute to human capital development, enabling individuals to diversify their income sources and build resilience against external shocks. Focusing on the interplay between assets, vulnerabilities, and institutional support, the SLF provides a holistic perspective on poverty reduction. It emphasises that effective poverty alleviation requires enhancing access to diverse assets, addressing systemic inequalities, and empowering communities to adapt to changing circumstances.

b. Human Capital Theory

Human Capital Theory, popularised by Becker (1993), underscores the importance of investments in education, skills, and health for enhancing productivity and economic outcomes. This theory posits that individuals are assets whose economic potential can be increased through proper investments in their capabilities. It links individual development to broader economic growth and poverty reduction efforts, providing a foundation for understanding how poverty alleviation programmes create long-term value.

According to this theory, education and skills acquisition are central to improving economic productivity. By equipping individuals with knowledge and technical skills, they become more competitive in the labour market and are better positioned to secure higher-paying jobs. Similarly, health is considered a crucial component of human capital, as healthier individuals are more productive and less likely to face financial hardships due to medical expenses or work incapacitation. Poverty alleviation programmes that align with Human Capital Theory often focus on building individual capacities. For instance, skill acquisition initiatives like the Youth Empowerment Scheme (YES) and the N-Power programme provide training in vocational and entrepreneurial skills, enabling beneficiaries to transition from unemployment to self-reliance. Additionally, healthcare-focused initiatives such as Conditional Cash Transfers (CCTs) that require beneficiaries to visit healthcare facilities address immediate health needs while fostering long-term productivity.

In Esan West Local Government Area, where limited access to quality education and healthcare perpetuates poverty, programmes that invest in human capital are particularly vital. By empowering individuals with the tools and resources to improve their circumstances, these initiatives contribute not only to individual welfare but also to the overall economic development of the region. This could be the reason why Oaikhena and Ikhayere (2023) observed that “an underdeveloped society or country is characterized by backwardness, primitiveness, tribalism, dependency, neo-colonialism, non-liberalism,

exploitation, late capitalism, lack of modern differentiated industries, state of poverty in the society, the domination of foreign capital in the hands of foreign and local bourgeoisie or local comprador, low technology, low level politics, including social and cultural development”.

c. Social Capital Theory

Social Capital Theory, as popularised by Putnam (2000), highlights the value derived from relationships, networks, and trust within communities. This theory emphasises that social connections facilitate cooperation and collective action, which are critical for achieving development goals. Unlike the other theories that focus primarily on individual resources and capabilities, Social Capital Theory underscores the role of community dynamics and social structures in poverty alleviation. The theory identifies networks, trust, and reciprocity as core elements of social capital. Networks provide access to resources, information, and opportunities that individuals might not otherwise have. Trust fosters cooperation and reduces transaction costs in economic and social interactions, while reciprocity promotes mutual support and resource sharing among community members.

Social Capital Theory is particularly relevant to poverty alleviation programmes that rely on community participation and collaboration. For example, microfinance initiatives that encourage group lending depend on social capital to ensure accountability and mutual support among participants. Similarly, cooperative farming schemes and community-based development projects leverage social networks to pool resources, share knowledge, and achieve common goals. These approaches are especially effective in rural areas like Esan West Local Government Area, where community ties often play a significant role in livelihood strategies.

Research Methodology

The research adopts a survey design to investigate the effect of poverty alleviation programmes in Esan West Local Government Area of Edo State. This design involves the use of structured questionnaire to collect data from a diverse group of respondents, including programme beneficiaries, community leaders, and policymakers. The survey approach is appropriate for this study as it allows for the collection of quantitative and qualitative data, enabling a comprehensive analysis of the programmes' outcomes.

The primary objective of this study is to evaluate the extent to which poverty alleviation programmes have addressed the multidimensional aspects of poverty in Esan West Local Government Area over the period 1999–2023 (24 years). By employing a survey design, the researchers gathered first-hand accounts of how these programmes have impacted income levels, employment opportunities, educational access, and living conditions. The data collected provided a nuanced understanding of the programmes' successes and the challenges faced during implementation.

This methodology ensures the reliability and validity of the research findings by employing systematic data collection and analysis techniques. The insights derived from this study would inform policymakers and development practitioners on strategies to improve the design and implementation of poverty alleviation programmes. The recommendations would aim to enhance the effectiveness, sustainability, and inclusivity of these programmes, thereby contributing to the broader goal of poverty reduction in Esan West Local Government Area and similar contexts across Nigeria.

The population for this research encompasses individuals or entities that meet the criteria for inclusion in the study (Adeosun & Udabah, 2017). The total population consists of residents and stakeholders in Esan West Local Government Area (LGA) of Edo State, estimated at one hundred and eighty-eight thousand seven hundred (188,700) (https://citypopulation.de/en/nigeria/admin/NGA012_edo/). As it focused on individuals such as beneficiaries of poverty alleviation programmes, local community leaders, programme facilitators, and government officials involved in implementation. These individuals provided critical insights into the design, implementation, and outcomes of

poverty alleviation programmes in the area. By examining their experiences, the study aims to uncover the effectiveness of these programmes in reducing poverty and improving the socioeconomic well-being of residents in Esan West Local Government Area. Given the large and diverse population of Esan West Local Government Area and the constraints of time and resources, a sample of 239 participants was selected. This sample includes individuals who have directly benefited from poverty alleviation programmes and key stakeholders such as programme facilitators and community representatives. The sample size is deemed sufficient to represent the broader population and ensures a practical and effective approach to data collection and analysis.

The sampling technique employed is purposive sampling, a non-probabilistic method selected for its ability to target participants with relevant experiences and exposure to poverty alleviation programmes. This approach ensures the inclusion of respondents who can provide detailed, context-specific data on the impact and challenges of these initiatives in Esan West Local Government Area. Therefore, for this research, the Taro Yamane formula was used for detecting the sample size. It states that:

$$N = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where N= Population size

e = significant level of error (0.05)

n= Sample size

For this research N= 188700

Therefore, the sample size:

$$n = \frac{188700}{1 + 188700(0.05)^2}$$

$$= \frac{188700}{427.75}$$

$$= 399.$$

~399 respondents

The research applied response rate of 60% of the respondents

To calculate 60% response rate of 400 respondents:

$$\text{Response Rate} = \frac{\text{Percentage}}{100} \times \text{Respondents}$$
$$\frac{60}{100} \times 399 = 239 \text{ respondents}$$

Out of 399 distributed questionnaires, 239 were completed and returned, resulting in a response rate of 60%. This response rate is considered adequate for statistical analysis and reflects a good level of engagement from the respondents. The high rate of return ensured that the data collected was representative and reliable for the study, minimising potential biases associated with non-response.

This study primarily utilises primary data collected directly from respondents within Esan West Local Government Area (LGA) of Edo State, Nigeria. Primary data refers to first-hand information specifically tailored to address the research objectives, providing accurate and relevant insights into the effect of poverty alleviation programmes in the region. Structured questionnaires serve as the primary data collection tool. These questionnaires are carefully crafted to gather essential information regarding the demographic characteristics of respondents, their socio-economic conditions, awareness and participation in poverty alleviation programmes, and the perceived impact of these programmes on their livelihoods. The questions are designed to elicit clear, quantifiable responses to ensure accuracy and facilitate a comprehensive analysis. Moreover, structured questionnaires offer several benefits, including standardisation, ease of administration, and the ability to collect data efficiently from a large sample size. This approach ensures that the data gathered aligns with the study's objectives and is reliable for drawing meaningful conclusions about the impact of poverty alleviation programmes on the residents of Esan West Local Government Area.

Data analysis involves examining, organising, and interpreting the collected data to answer research questions and test hypotheses. In this study, a combination of simple percentage analysis and statistical techniques were used to ensure effective and accurate interpretation of the data gathered through the questionnaire. Simple percentage analysis was applied to summarise the responses for each item on the questionnaire. This method allowed for clear representation of the data in percentage form, making it easier to identify trends and key observations among the respondents. Each questionnaire item was

assigned a score, and the total scores were calculated to generate a quantitative summary of the data.

In addition to percentage analysis, the mean score method was used to calculate the average responses for each item. This provided a measure of central tendency, offering insights into the general opinions and perceptions of the respondents. However, for a complex data analysis of this nature, the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 was utilised. SPSS is powerful statistical software that supports various statistical methods and allows for efficient handling of large datasets. Through SPSS, the researcher performed descriptive statistics, created charts, and generated graphs, which provided a clearer understanding of the research findings. The combination of these analytical tools ensured that the data was thoroughly analysed, enabling the researcher to draw meaningful conclusions and formulate actionable recommendations

Hypotheses Testing

H0: Poverty alleviation programmes have a significant positive impact on household income in Esan West Local Government Area.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	29903.224	1	29903.224	69.934	.004 ^b
	Residual	1282.776	3	427.592		
	Total	31186.000	4			

Source: Researcher's Computation

a. Dependent Variable: House hold income

b. Predictors: (Constant), Poverty alleviation

The results of the ANOVA test show that poverty alleviation programmes have a significant positive impact on household income in Esan West Local Government Area. With a **p-value** of 0.004, which is less than the commonly accepted significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis (H0) is rejected. This indicates that there is strong statistical evidence to support the claim that poverty alleviation programmes positively affect

household income. The high F-value (69.934) further suggests a substantial and statistically significant relationship between the programmes and increased household income. This finding implies that participation in poverty alleviation efforts contributes to improvements in the financial stability of the households involved.

H0₂: Poverty alleviation programmes increased employment opportunities for beneficiaries in Esan West Local Government Area.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	69736.265	1	69736.265	8.859	.059 ^b
	Residual	23614.935	3	7871.645		
	Total	93351.200	4			

Source: Researcher's Computation

a. Dependent Variable: Employment opportunities

b. Predictors: (Constant), Poverty alleviation programmes

In this case, the ANOVA results show that the p-value is 0.059, which is slightly above the 0.05 threshold for statistical significance. This means that the evidence is not strong enough to reject the null hypothesis (H0₂). While the F-value (8.859) suggests that there is some variation explained by the poverty alleviation programmes, the p-value indicates that the effect of these programmes on employment opportunities is not statistically significant at the 5% significance level. Therefore, the hypothesis that poverty alleviation programmes significantly increase employment opportunities for beneficiaries in Esan West Local Government Area is not supported by the data.

H0₃: Poor implementation of poverty alleviation programmes is negatively correlated with the success of these initiatives in Esan West Local Government Area.

		ANOVA ^a			
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	27457.397	1	27457.397	1.120	.321 ^b
Residual	196202.603	8	24525.325		
Total	223660.000	9			

Source: Researcher's Computation

a. Dependent Variable: Success initiatives

b. Predictors: (Constant), Poverty alleviation programme

For this hypothesis, the ANOVA test results show a very high p-value of 0.321, which is well above the 0.05 significance level. This means that the evidence is insufficient to reject the null hypothesis (H_0). The F-value of 1.120 further supports the conclusion that the relationship between poor implementation and the success of poverty alleviation programmes is not statistically significant. Therefore, the data does not provide strong support for the idea that poor implementation is negatively correlated with the success of these programmes. This suggests that other factors might be influencing the success of poverty alleviation programmes in Esan West Local Government Area, rather than implementation quality alone.

H04: The living standards of beneficiaries in Esan West Local Government Area improve as a result of participating in poverty alleviation programmes.

<i>Model</i>	ANOVA^a				
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
1 Regression	103372.431	1	103372.431	36.667	.009 ^b
Residual	8457.569	3	2819.190		
Total	111830.000	4			

Source: Researcher's Computation

a. Dependent Variable: Standard of living

b. Predictors: (Constant), Poverty alleviation programme

The results for this hypothesis show a p-value of 0.009, which is below the 0.05 threshold for significance, indicating that there is a statistically significant relationship between participation in poverty alleviation programmes and the improvement of beneficiaries' living standards. The F-value of 36.667 is quite high, suggesting that the poverty alleviation programmes have a strong effect on the living standards of those involved. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis that poverty alleviation programmes improve the living standards of beneficiaries in Esan West Local Government Area is supported. This finding revealed the positive impact of these programmes on the quality of life for the people who participate in them.

Summary of Findings

The analysis of poverty alleviation programmes in Esan West Local Government Area presents empirical results on their effectiveness, challenges, and perceived impact. The findings are structured based on thematic areas drawn from the descriptive statistics presented in the study. The bio-data analysis reveals that the sample population in this study is diverse in terms of gender, marital status, education, and length of residence. The majority of respondents are female, married, with secondary school education, and have lived in Edo State for over a decade. These demographic factors could potentially influence the respondents' views on the effectiveness of poverty alleviation programmes,

suggesting that different socio-economic backgrounds may result in varying experiences and outcomes related to the programmes.

The data reveals that poverty alleviation programmes have not substantially improved household income among beneficiaries. Responses indicate a limited perception of reduced reliance on external financial support. Participants agreed to some extent that these programmes address immediate family needs through financial support. However, significant scepticism exists regarding the programmes' ability to deliver consistent income growth or long-term financial stability. This suggests that the interventions might lack the scope or sustainability necessary to bring about meaningful and lasting economic change for participants.

Poverty alleviation programmes were perceived as moderately effective in creating employment opportunities. Skills acquisition initiatives were noted as particularly important in enhancing employability. However, other dimensions, such as job relevance to qualifications and the promotion of self-employment, were less successful, suggesting challenges in aligning these opportunities with participants' skills and aspirations. Furthermore, while some respondents acknowledged the programmes' role in reducing unemployment at the community level, the individual benefits were not as widely experienced.

The study identified several challenges hindering the effectiveness of poverty alleviation programmes. Corruption and mismanagement of funds were rated as significant obstacles. Respondents also highlighted inadequate funding and biases in beneficiary selection as critical issues. Administrative delays and limited community involvement further compounded these challenges, reducing the programmes' inclusivity, transparency, and efficiency. These findings point to systemic issues that require urgent attention to enhance the effectiveness of poverty alleviation efforts.

Poverty alleviation programmes showed limited success in improving participants' living standards. While some respondents acknowledged slight improvements in their overall standard of living, the perceived impact on specific areas, such as access to quality healthcare, housing affordability, and education, was modest at best. The most concerning result was the minimal impact on addressing nutritional needs.

This shortfall in meeting a basic necessity undermines the overall effectiveness of the interventions.

The success or failure of poverty alleviation programmes was found to be influenced by several factors. Effective community involvement emerged as the most significant factor, underscoring the importance of participatory approaches in programme design and implementation. Poor monitoring and evaluation systems and cultural or societal factors were also identified as major contributors to programme failure. Government commitment and funding, though critical, were perceived as inadequate, while collaboration with local organisations was seen as having room for improvement in fostering partnerships.

Conclusion

The findings of this study revealed the mixed effectiveness of poverty alleviation programmes in Esan West Local Government Area, Edo State. While these programmes offer some temporary relief for basic needs and moderately address unemployment at the community level, they fail to achieve significant and sustainable improvements in household income and overall living standards. Despite some perceived benefits, challenges such as corruption, inadequate funding, administrative delays, and limited community involvement continue to undermine their effectiveness. Moreover, the absence of robust monitoring and evaluation frameworks exacerbates these issues, making it difficult to identify gaps and implement necessary improvements.

The study also revealed systemic inefficiencies in programme design, including the misalignment of job opportunities with participants' skills and qualifications. This mismatch not only limits the potential for self-employment and entrepreneurship but also contributes to underemployment and dissatisfaction among beneficiaries.

Crucially, the study emphasises the pivotal role of community participation and cultural sensitivity in ensuring the success of poverty alleviation efforts. Greater collaboration with local stakeholders, combined with a participatory approach to planning and implementation, can enhance the relevance, inclusivity, and effectiveness of these initiatives. By aligning programmes with the socio-economic realities and cultural

dynamics of the target population, poverty alleviation efforts can achieve more meaningful and lasting impacts, ultimately fostering sustainable development in Esan West Local Government Area.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed to improve the effectiveness of poverty alleviation programmes in Esan West Local Government Area:

- i. The government should prioritise increased and consistent funding for poverty alleviation programmes. Transparent allocation of resources and the establishment of accountability mechanisms are essential to ensure that funds reach intended beneficiaries and address key needs effectively.
- ii. Incorporating community members in the planning, implementation, and monitoring of poverty alleviation programmes is crucial. This participatory approach fosters a sense of ownership, ensures that initiatives are tailored to local needs, and improves programme relevance and acceptance.
- iii. Anti-corruption measures, such as regular audits and the use of technology to track resource allocation, should be implemented to reduce the diversion of funds. Establishing independent oversight committees can further enhance transparency and accountability in programme management.
- iv. Robust monitoring and evaluation frameworks should be developed to track programme progress and measure outcomes. This will help identify gaps, assess the impact of interventions, and guide evidence-based decision-making for future programmes.

References

- Akpan, G. (2019). Targeting efficiency in poverty alleviation programmes in Nigeria: Challenges and prospects. *Journal of Development Policy*, 12(3), 45–62.
- Akpan, T. (2019). Understanding poverty reduction strategies in Nigeria: An analysis of NAPEP. *African Journal of Economic Development*, 8(3), 34–48.
- Babatunde, R. O., Omotesho, O. A., & Sholotan, O. S. (2021). Agricultural support programmes and poverty alleviation in rural Nigeria. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 42(2), 45–58.
- Babatunde, R. O., Omotesho, O. A., & Sholotan, O. S. (2021). The impact of poverty alleviation programmes in rural Nigeria. *Journal of Rural Development Studies*, 16(2), 55–70.
- Bello, M., & Oyinlola, A. (2019). Challenges facing rural poverty alleviation in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Development Economics*, 22(4), 45–62.
- Bello, M., & Oyinlola, A. (2019). Challenges facing poverty alleviation programmes in Nigeria. *Journal of African Studies*, 12(4), 56–70.
- Edo State Bureau of Statistics. (2021). *Agricultural support programmes and rural development in Esan West LGA*. Edo State Government Press.
- Edo State Bureau of Statistics. (2021). *Socioeconomic profile of Esan West LGA*. Edo State Government Press.
- National Bureau of Statistics [NBS]. (2022). *Poverty and inequality in Nigeria: 2022 report*. NBS Press.
- Oaikhena, I. M. (2021). Reinforcement of humanitarian policies to AID displaced population in Nigeria and Africa through coordination, collaboration and integration mechanism. *International Journal of Social Science And Human Research (IJSSHR)*. Vol. 04 Issue 12 3998-4003
- Oaikhena, I. M. & Aligbe, A. B. (2023). Rethinking redistributive policies for regulatory compliance in a democratic developing society. *Singaporean Journal of Business Economics and Management. (Sing. J. Bus. Eco. & Mng)*. 9(2). 59-66.
- Oaikhena, I. M. (2021). Policy pathways towards poverty reduction in the midst of covid-19 pandemic in Africa: the case of Nigeria and Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC). *Pandemic in the 21st Century: Multidimensional Approaches 2nd College of Management and Social Sciences 2021 Conference*. 212-222.
- Oaikhena, I. M. & Idehen, R. (2021). Personnel management and the challenges of Local Government in Nigeria: Issues and prospects. *NOUN International Journal of Peace Studies and Conflict Resolution [INIJPCR]* Vol. 1, No. 1, 186-202.
- Oaikhena, I. M. & Ikhayere, A. (2023). Infringement on fundamental human rights through human trafficking. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (Kuwait Chapter) AJBMR*. 12(2) 35-44.
- Ojo, M., & Adeyemi, F. (2021). Youth empowerment programmes and economic sustainability in Nigeria: The role of N-Power. *Journal of Youth Development Studies*, 15(2), 22–39.